

Early intervention with Cognitive Behavioral Therapy reduces sick leave duration in people with adjustment, anxiety and depressive disorders.

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Abstract

Background: Early intervention in workers diagnosed with mental disorders is associated with a lower incidence of relapse and shorter sick leave. However, no studies have been carried out on the effect of early intervention using an evidence-based therapy, Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT), on people with sick leave. Aims: The objectives of the present study are to study whether the type of intervention (early or late) will affect the total duration of the sick leave, the partial duration of the sick leave, the duration of the psychotherapy, and the time until return to work after the psychotherapy ends. The sample was composed of 167 participants who were on sick leave for adjustment disorders, anxiety disorders, or depressive disorder. Results: The participants who had early intervention with CBT had a significantly shorter duration of total sick leave and partial sick leave, and a shorter time until returning to work after the psychotherapy ended than those who had late intervention. There were no statistically differences in the duration or efficacy of the psychotherapy. Conclusions: We can suggest that providing early access to CBT significantly reduces the length of sick leave in patients with mental disorders.

Keys Words: Sick leave, return to work, cognitive behavioral therapy, adjustment disorders, anxiety disorders, depressive disorders

Studies with workers on sick leave for depression, anxiety, and stress-related disorders have found that people diagnosed with common mental disorders were less likely to return to work (Alexanderson & Norlund, 2004; Andersen, Nielsen, & Brinkmann, 2014; Blank, Peters, Pickvance, Wilford, & Macdonald, 2008; González-Barcala et al., 2006; Koopmans et al., 2011; Layard & Clark, 2015; Royo-Bordonada, 1999; Vaez et al., 2007). These pathologies make up 3.48% of the illnesses requiring sick leave, and 5.13% of the total days of sick leave (Vicente-Herrero, Terradillos García, Capdevila Garcia, Ramírez Iñiguez De La Torre, & López-González, 2013). In general, people with mental disorders have longer sick leaves than if they had a physical health problem (Flach, Groothoff, Krol, & Bültmann, 2012; Øyeflaten, Lie, Ihlebæk, & Eriksen, 2014; Van der Feltz-Cornelis et al. (2010). Therefore, mental health disorders are associated with a greater risk of long-term illness, permanent disability (Catalina-Romero et al, 2013; Knudsen et al., 2010; Naidu, Giblin, Burke, & Madan, 2016; Soósová, Macejová, Zamboriová, & Dimunová, 2017), and relapse (Arends, van der Klink, van Rhenen, de Boer, & Bültmann, 2014; Dewa, Chau, & Dermer, 2009; Koopmans et al., 2011). In fact, approximately 20-30% of workers with anxiety and depression disorders experience a relapse after returning to work (Prang, Bohensky, Smith, & Collie, 2016).

It has been widely recognized that reducing the number of days a worker is on sick leave due to a health problem is an objective shared by the company, the public healthcare system, and the worker, due to the strong impact on all of them. Although sick leave may have several positive consequences (Vingård, Alexanderson, & Norlund, 2004), being unemployed also tends to have negative consequences for the worker because work is part of his/her social network and allows the construction of identity, which is beneficial for mental health and general well-being (Andersen et al.,

2014; Fimland et al., 2014). Caring for people with mental disorders as a top priority is an objective established by different European countries (Martin, Nielsen, Petersen, Jakobsen, & Rugulies, 2012; van der Klink, Blonk, Schene, & van Dijk, 2003). The absence of disease and the return to work are multifactorial phenomena, influenced by the clinical improvement of the patient and the personal characteristics of the worker, expectations, the workplace and the health system. However, the specialized literature expresses strong agreement about the importance of referring patients with mental disorders as soon as the need is detected (Cornelius, van der Klink, Groothoff, & Brouwer, 2011; Flach et al., 2012). In fact, early intervention on factors that can be modified is recommended (Vlasveld et al., 2013), and clinical treatment has been found to have better results and greater success in patients with anxiety and depression disorders if they have access to it in the first weeks (Dewa, Hoch, Carmen, Guscott, & Anderson, 2009; Pomaki, Franche, & Murray, 2012; Sogaard & Bech, 2009; Wang et al., 2007), but it is less effective in the case of psychiatric disorders (Nieuwenhuijsen, Verbeek, De Boer, Blonk, & Van Dijk, 2004). Early intervention in workers diagnosed with common mental disorders is associated with a lower incidence of relapse, which is beneficial for the worker, the company, and society in general (Hoefsmit, Houkes, & Nijhuis, 2012). Moreover, a review study found early intervention to be a key issue in reducing work absenteeism (Gabbay et al., 2011).

There are different definitions of early intervention. Some studies consider that early intervention occurs when the treatment begins before the second week or 14 days from the beginning of sick leave (van Beurden et al., 2013; Lammerts, van Dongen, Schaafsma, van Mechelen, & Anema, 2017; van der Klink et al., 2003), in the third week (Brouwers, Terluin, Tiemens, & Verhaak, 2009), before the first month (Roelen et al., 2012), in the fourth week, as the Swedish legislation stipulates (Burstrom, Nylen,

Clayton, & Whitehead, 2011), or before the sixth week, as stated in the Dutch Law on Gatekeeper Improvement (Cornelius et al., 2011; Flach et al., 2012; Hoefsmit et al., 2012; Rebergen, Bruinvels, Bos, van der Beek, & van Mechelen, 2010).

Some studies confirm the effectiveness of early intervention by a mental health specialist in cases of sick leave (e.g., Naidu et al., 2016). Clinical guidelines in many countries (e.g. Salomonsson, Hedman-Lagerlöf, & Öst, 2018) conclude that psychological treatments, primarily Cognitive Behavioral Therapy (CBT), are effective in treating mental disorders (National Institute for Health & Clinical Excellence [NICE], 2004, 2005, 2011). However, to the best of our knowledge, no studies have been carried out on the effect of early intervention using evidence-based therapies, such as CBT, with people diagnosed with adjustment, anxiety, and depressive disorders on sick leave.

Thus, the objectives of the present study are to study whether the type of intervention (early or late) will affect the total duration of the sick leave, the partial duration of the sick leave, the duration of the psychotherapy, and the time until return to work after the psychotherapy ends. Another objective is to find out whether the type of intervention (early or late) will affect the efficacy of the treatment.

Method

Sample

The participants in the study were sequentially recruited between June 1st 2015 and November 30th 2016 in a collaborative Social Security Insurance Group in Spain that evaluates and treats workers when they are on sick leave. The inclusion criteria were: a) Participants of both sexes between 18 and 65 years old in a situation of sick leave who voluntarily accepted CBT treatment; b) met the DSM-IV-TR for Depressive Disorders,

Adjustment Disorders, and Anxiety Disorders; and c) ended the treatment after reaching clinical improvement and returned to work.

Participants were excluded from the study if they were already being treated by another specialist, they had more than one main medical diagnosis, their process was being addressed legally, or they had been diagnosed with personality disorders.

Participants were European Whites, and participation was voluntary. Informed consent was given by participants.

As table 1 shows, the final sample was composed of 167 participants with the following diagnoses: 60.5%, $n = 101$, met the criteria for Adjustment Disorders; 24.6%, $n = 41$, for Anxiety Disorders; and 15%, $n = 25$, for Depressive Disorders. In this sample, 68.9 % ($n = 115$) were women and 31.1% ($n = 52$) men. Participants' age range was broad, 18-65 years old, with an average age of 42.16 ($SD = 9.91$) years, the participants with early intervention presented an average age of 40.45 years ($SD = 8.34$), and the participants with late intervention presented an average age of 42.42 years ($SD = 10.12$). 32.3 % ($n = 54$) had a primary education level, 39.5% ($n = 66$) a secondary education level, 15 % ($n = 25$) mid-level university, and 13.2 % ($n = 22$) high-level university. Table 2 shows the socio-occupational characteristics of the sample.

Measures

Structured Clinical Interview for DSM-IV Axis I disorders (SCID I; First, Spitzer, Gibbon, & Williams 1995). This instrument makes it possible to obtain the main Axis I diagnoses according to the DSM-IV-TR (APA, 2000). It presents adequate psychometric properties with high reliability for the different diagnoses (Kappa = .66-.83) (Lobbestael, Leurgans, & Arntz, 2011).

Beck Depression Inventory-II (BDI-II; Beck, Steer & Brown, 1996). This inventory consists of 21 items with four response alternatives (0-4) that rate depressive

symptomatology. Its Spanish version offers good psychometric properties (Sanz, García-Vera, Espinosa, Fortun & Vazquez, 2005). In our sample, it presented adequate reliability ($\alpha = .93$).

Beck Anxiety Inventory (BAI; Beck, & Steer, 1993). We utilized the Spanish adaptation of the BAI (Sanz & Navarro, 2003). This inventory consists of 21 items with four response alternatives (0-4) to assess anxiety symptoms. In our sample, excellent internal consistency was found on the pre-treatment assessment ($\alpha = .91$) and on the post-treatment assessment ($\alpha = .91$).

In addition, an ad hoc instrument was constructed for this study to collect demographic, job, and clinical data. Dates were obtained with which to calculate the following indicators: a) Time before beginning psychotherapy: the time elapsed between the initial date of the sick leave and beginning psychotherapy. This time period was not controlled by the experimental design. This time delay depends on external factors related to the organization of social security and public mental health services ; b) Total duration of the sick leave: the number of days between the beginning and end of the sick leave; c) Partial duration of the sick leave: the number of days of sick leave minus the delay in referral, that is, the days between the date of referral to the psychologist and the return to work; e) Duration of the psychotherapy: the number of days between the dates of beginning and ending psychotherapy; and f) Time until return to work after the psychotherapy ends: the number of days between the date of the end of psychotherapy and the date of the return to work.

Procedure.

The study had the approval of the Regional Ethics Committee on Clinical Studies (CAEC) of the Valencia Government, Spain (UCV/2014-2015/13). First, we

used email to contact 20 clinical psychologists, associated with a collaborative Social Security Insurance Group, who usually care for patients on sick leave for mental disorders, and we requested their collaboration on the project. Eighteen psychologists from twelve different provinces in Spain agreed in writing to be a collaborating researcher to collect the sample. They were experts in CBT with more than 10 years of experience. We sent the assessment and therapeutic protocols to the psychologists by ordinary mail and in an online version. They included all the procedures to be applied, the pre and post questionnaires, and the data collection form.

When the workers feel symptoms of depression or anxiety, they request a visit with a medical doctor in the Spanish Public Health System. The medical doctor grants the worker a sick leave certificate, based on the diagnosis with the SCID (First et al., 1995), and refers the worker to psychotherapy with a mental health specialist psychologist. The sick leave certificate, the diagnosis, and the decision that the worker would return to work (end of sick leave) were established by an independent evaluator, not associated with our study, who was a medical doctor in the Spanish Public Health System, using the SCID (First et al., 1995). Psychotherapeutic treatment and sick leave certification were separate from each other. Participants who met the criteria for Depressive Disorders, Adjustment Disorders, and/or Anxiety Disorders were directly referred for psychological therapy. In the first session, the psychologist offered the patient the possibility of participating in the study. Two hundred participants were consulted, and 167 (83.5%) agreed to participate and filled in the BDI and BAI questionnaires on the first day (pre-test). To ensure that the treatment applied by the therapists was uniform, protocols of manualized treatment were prepared ad hoc for this investigation, based on clinical manuals of CBT published in Spain following the recommendations of the National Institute for Health and Clinical Excellence [NICE]

(2004, 2005, 2011). The therapeutic intervention consisted of the application of the individual psychological program based on CBT protocol, adapted to the particular needs of the patient. The psychotherapeutic treatment with CBT had both a work-focus and a focus on symptom reduction. The main objective of the CBT psychotherapy was to train participants to cope with stressful situations in their workplace and overcome internal and external problems that keep them from returning to their jobs. This objective was achieved through the individual therapy sessions, which consisted of: (a) an introduction to CBT; (b) psychoeducation about anxiety, stress, and depression; (c) identification of dysfunctional beliefs as main causal factors of anxiety or depression; (d) modification of dysfunctional thinking; (e) increasing pleasurable everyday activities; (f) training in problem solving techniques; (g) training in communication skills; (h) implementation of strategies at work; and (i) relapse prevention.

The psychotherapy sessions were held weekly and lasted 50-60 minutes. The number of sessions was not previously established and depended on the needs of the participants. All the therapists received training in the application of the manuals created ad hoc for this research. The principal researcher conducted supervisory sessions to verify that all the investigators applied the treatment in the same way. In the supervisory sessions, the researcher evaluated the objective of the psychotherapy, the strategies used, the skills learned, and the patient's improvement, etc. Once the therapeutic objectives agreed upon with the patient had been achieved and the patient was functionally able to return to his/her usual work, the participants filled out the BDI and BAI questionnaires (post-test). All the participants and the psychologists were blind to the study aims and design. All the workers on sick leave received the economic compensation established by Spanish labor laws.

Statistical procedure.

First, to calculate whether there were differences in the delay in beginning psychotherapy depending on the diagnosis, an ANOVA was performed with a post hoc Tukey test. Second, the sample was statistically divided into two groups by the researcher at the end of the treatment. The early intervention group was composed of participants who had their first psychotherapy session before day 14 of the sick leave, and the late intervention group was composed of participants who had their first psychotherapy session after day 14 of the sick leave. Day 14 was chosen as a cut-off point based on the recommendations of authors such as van Beurden et al., (2013), Lammerts et al., (2017), and van der Klink et al., (2003). To confirm that there were no differences before starting the treatment depending on the type of intervention (early vs late) on the anxiety and depression measures, a Student's t test was performed for independent samples, and several χ^2 were performed for socio-occupational variables. Then, Student's t test for independent samples was used to discover whether there were differences depending on the type of intervention (early vs late) on the variables of total duration of the sick leave, partial duration of the sick leave, time until returning to work after finishing the psychotherapy, and duration of the psychotherapy. Finally, to find out whether the type of intervention (early or late) affected the efficacy of the intervention for the anxiety and depression symptomatology of the participants, a repeated-measures ANOVA was performed.

Results

The mean Time before beginning psychotherapy for the whole sample was $M = 47.49$ ($SD = 47.07$) days. The anxiety disorders presented $M = 52.22$ ($SD = 47.04$), the depressive disorders $M = 46.86$ ($SD = 29.71$), and the adjustment disorders $M = 45.5$ ($SD = 50.3$). However, there were no statistically significant differences in the Time

before beginning psychotherapy ($F_{(2,165)} = .316; p = .729$) based on the diagnosis. As table 3 shows, regarding the timing of the intervention, 86.8%, $n = 145$, of the participants had a late intervention, that is, beginning psychotherapy after day 14 of their sick leave, with a mean of 53.21 (47.98) days, and 13.2 %, $n = 22$, had an early intervention, that is, beginning psychotherapy before day 14, with a mean of 9.82 (3.49) days. There were no differences in anxiety ($t_{(166)} = .59; p = .55$), depression ($t_{(166)} = 1.54; p = .12$), gender ($\chi^2(1) = .158, p = .69$), educational level ($\chi^2(3) = 2.26, p = .52$), diagnosis ($\chi^2(2) = 3.89, p = .14$), job held ($\chi^2(2) = 3.60, p = .16$), seniority in job ($\chi^2(5) = 5.32, p = .38$), job sector ($\chi^2(10) = 11.92, p = .29$), or form of payment ($\chi^2(2) = 3.63, p = .16$) between the early and late intervention groups before beginning treatment.

As table 3 shows, the participants with early intervention presented a shorter total duration of sick leave than the participants with late intervention. The difference, 80.69 days, was statistically significant ($t_{(62,28)} = -5.94; p < .001$). The participants with early intervention presented a shorter partial duration of sick leave than participants with late intervention. The difference was 37 days and statistically significant ($t_{(50,885)} = -2.874; p = .006$). Participants with early intervention presented a shorter psychotherapy duration than participants with late intervention. Although the participants with early intervention had shorter treatments, this difference (13.61 days) was not statistically significant ($t_{(164)} = -0.867; p = .387$). The participants with early intervention had less time until return to work after the psychotherapy ended than participants in the late intervention group. The difference between the two groups was 33.26 days and statistically significant ($t_{(67,753)} = -3.851; p = .001$).

As table 4 shows, regarding the anxiety symptoms, in the early and late intervention participants, there were statistically significant improvements between before and after the CBT psychotherapy ($F_{(1,161)} = 108.74, p = .001, \eta^2 = .41$), although

there were no statistically significant differences between the groups at the end of treatment ($F_{(1,161)} = 108.74, p = .273$). On the depressive symptoms, in the participants with early intervention and late intervention, there were statistically significant improvements between before and after the treatment ($F_{(1,161)} = 166.08, p = .001, \eta^2 = .51$). However, there were no statistically significant differences between the two groups after ending treatment ($F_{(1,161)} = .31, p = .0861$).

Discussion

The objectives of our study were: to study whether the type of intervention (early or late) affected the total duration of sick leave, the partial duration of sick leave, the duration of the psychotherapy, and the time until return to work after the psychotherapy ends. Moreover, another objective was to find out whether the type of intervention (early or late) affected the efficacy of the treatment.

In the present study, we found statistically significant differences in the total duration of sick leave depending on the type of intervention. In other words, the participants who had early intervention with CBT had a significantly shorter sick leave than those who had late intervention, specifically 80 days less. These results agree with a previous study where the delay in referring the participants to CBT predicted the total length of non work-related sick leave (Alonso, Marco & Andani, 2017). In addition, other authors (Brouwers et al., 2009; Hoefsmit et al., 2012; van Beurden et al., 2013; Rebergen et al., 2010.; Nieuwenhuijsen, Verbeek, Siemerink, & Tummers-Nijssen, 2003) found that a 2-3 week delay in receiving care from a healthcare specialist (doctors, occupational doctors, psychiatrists) lengthened sick leave. Along the same lines, our study coincides with van der Feltz- Cornelis et al. (2010), who indicated that psychiatric intervention helped to achieve an earlier return to work, and suggested that the treatment would have been more efficacious if it had begun earlier. Moreover, the

average sick-leave duration until return to work for the early intervention group was shorter than the average sick leave duration until return to work after clinical or work-focused interventions in meta-analytic studies about interventions for enhancing return to work in individuals with a common mental illness, for example, 151 days shorter (Nigatu et al., 2016).

In our study, we found significant differences in the partial duration of the sick leave depending on the type of intervention. That is, if we subtract the time elapsed until referring the person to psychotherapy and count the number of days of sick leave from the moment of beginning the psychotherapy, the mean duration of the sick leave with early intervention was shorter than with late intervention, specifically 37 days less. Therefore, we can indicate that early intervention significantly reduces the length of sick leave. Our data agree with other authors who state that early intervention would help to shorten the duration of sick leave (e.g. Brouwers et al., 2009).

Shorter sick leave implies a reduction in the worker's suffering, which is a fundamental aspect from a clinical and human point of view, and it reduces the associated economic costs and decreases isolation and separation from the work setting (Ayuso-Mateos, Nieto-Moreno, Sánchez-Moreno, & Vázquez-Barquero, 2006). Therefore, there is a greater possibility of returning to the job market, less likelihood of suffering permanent disability, and, finally, lower economic costs for the company, social security, and society in general (Bultmann, Christensen, Burr, Lund, & Rugulies, 2008; Gjesdal & Bratberg, 2003).

With regard to the duration of the psychotherapy, the results show that there are no significant differences based on the type of intervention. Regardless of the type of intervention, early or late, the treatment lasted the same amount of time. These data indicate that although the participating psychologists had the freedom to devote more or

less time to each patient depending on his/her specific needs, they used a similar number of days, regardless of the referral delay. These results follow along the lines of those from the study by Alonso et al., (2017), where there were no differences in the treatment based on the type of intervention.

With regard to the time until return to work after the psychotherapy, we found significant differences in this time period depending on the type of intervention. Thus, in the case of early intervention, the return to work occurs even before the psychological treatment is over. However, in the case of late intervention, the return to work occurs after the treatment is over. Specifically, there is a difference of 33 days of sick leave between the participants in the early and late referral groups. These results coincide with other previous studies (Alonso et al., 2017) showing that the delay in referral to CBT was positively associated with the return to work after finishing the psychological treatment. We want to emphasize this result because early referral to psychotherapy produces a greater reduction in return to work days than the reduction in days found in meta-analyses about reducing return to work after psychological intervention or interventions by occupational health services in workers with mental disorders on sick leave, that is, 13 days (Nigatu et al., 2016) and 6.6 days (Doki, Sasahara, & Matsuzaki, 2015).

Regarding the efficacy of the intervention, we found that at the end of the CBT and at the moment of returning to work, all the participants, those with early intervention and those with late intervention, experienced a statistically significant improvement in the anxiety and depression symptoms. It is important to test the efficacy of the intervention because, even though the person returned to work, this does not always mean that the intervention was effective. As various authors have indicated (e.g. Alonso et al,

2017), one of the limitations of studies that analyze the factors influencing the return to work is that they do not test the efficacy of the intervention performed.

The results found in our study may be due, in part, to the fact that initiating treatment early can produce greater patient involvement and stronger treatment adherence because patients may have more positive expectations about their recovery than those who start their treatment later. Participants' expectations about when they will return to work is a better predictor of returning to the job world than the predictions of healthcare professionals (Løvvik, Øverland, Hysing, Broadbent, & Reme, 2014; Nieuwenhuijsen, Verbeek, de Boer, Blonk, & van Dijk, 2006). Therefore, having positive expectations of self-efficacy and perceiving that their disorder is more controllable or curable predict an earlier return to work (Broadbent, Kydd, Sanders, & Vanderpyl, 2008 ; Brouwers et al., 2009; Cornelius et al., 2011; Volker, Zijlstra-Vlasveld, Brouwers, van Lomwel, & van der Feltz-Cornelis, 2015), and our results are consistent with these studies.

Another result that emerges from this study is that, regardless of the diagnosis people have, they are referred to treatment at the same time. However, studies indicate that the mean length of sick leave is usually greater in people with a diagnosis of depression than in people with other diagnoses (Blank et al., 2008; Nielsen et al., 2011). Although the difference found in our study was not significant, patients diagnosed with a depressive disorder were referred earlier than those with anxiety disorders, and quite close to those with adaptive disorders. In addition, the effects of the diagnosis on the patients, and even on the professionals who treat them, which have been addressed in some studies (Flach et al., 2012; Rymaszewska et al., 2007), were not observed here. In other words, the expectations of the patient and the doctor about recovery and clinical deterioration depending on the diagnosis have not been described because an early or late beginning of treatment was not modulated by this variable. As far as we know, no studies have

explicitly compared the differential access to treatment based on the diagnosis (Burstrom et al., 2011).

The main limitation of the present study is the size of the groups after dividing the sample according to when psychotherapy began. Although the initial sample is adequate ($n = 167$), when it is divided, two unequal groups are formed, with the late intervention group being much larger than the early intervention group. However, we found no differences between the groups on anxiety and depression symptoms before the treatment, and so they can be considered similar in terms of clinical and socio-occupational characteristics. This difference between the participants with early vs late intervention occurs because our criterion was quite stringent, as we defined early referral as occurring before 14 days. Our decision was based on ethical and clinical motives, as well as the indications of other authors (van Beurden et al., 2013; Lammerts et al., 2017; van der Klink et al., 2003). Therefore, future research should replicate this study with a larger sample in order to obtain more representative samples after forming the groups, for example, by considering gender, broadening the inclusion criteria to observe other mental disorders, and performing a follow-up after the return to work to register relapses. Another limitation is that the present study is a longitudinal observational study, which means that we cannot talk about causality between variables. Moreover, the study design was retrospective, and so the results obtained can be considered in terms of correlates rather than causal risk factors. Future research should confirm these results in a randomized control trial. Moreover, in this study we did not control the delay patients experienced in being seen by the medical doctor from Spanish Public Health System who assessed and referred them to psychotherapy. In future research, this delay should be controlled. Finally, another limitation is that in the late intervention group, psychotherapy lasted more than three months, and we did not

control whether the duration of the psychotherapy might even keep patients from going back to work. Meta-analytic studies found that psychological treatments reduced (e.g. Van Der Klink et al., 2003) or prevented (Hägglund et al., 2014) sick leave in some studies, but in other studies they did not (Ejeby et al., 2014). Therefore, future research should analyze whether psychotherapy could make it difficult for patients to return to work.

The present study indicates how we can help to prevent long-term sick leave by influencing precisely those variables that we can modify (Vlasveld et al., 2013), such as access to specialized treatment in the initial phases of sick leave (Dewa et al., 2009; Lee, Rothbard, & Choi, 2016; Pomaki et al., 2012; Sogaard & Bech, 2009; Wang et al., 2007).

We can conclude that speeding up the management of sick leaves and providing early access to CBT applied by healthcare psychologists significantly reduces the duration of sick leave due to common mental disorders.

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Table 1

Sociodemographic variables of the sample.

Variables		Overall sample		Early intervention		Late Intervention	
		<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
Gender	Men	52	31.1	8	36.4	44	30.3
	Women	115	68.9	14	63.6	101	69.7
Educational level	Primary	54	32.3	5	22.7	49	33.8
	Secondary	66	39.5	8	36.4	58	40
	Mid-level university	25	15.0	4	18.2	21	14.5
	High-level university	22	13.2	5	22.7	17	11.7
Diagnosis	Adaptive Disorders	101	60.5	17	77.3	83	57.2
	Affective Disorders	25	15.0	1	4.5	21	14.5
	Anxiety Disorders	41	24.6	4	18.2	41	28.3

Table 2

Socio-occupational characteristics of the sample.

		Overall sample		Early intervention		Late intervention	
		n	%	n	%	n	%
Job held	First level: laborer, worker	142	85.0	17	77.3	125	86.2
	Second level: boss, supervisor	21	12.6	5	22.7	16	11
	Third level: head boss	4	2.4	0	0	4	2.8
	Fourth level: top executive	0	0	0	0	0	0
Seniority in job	Less than 3 months.	2	1.2	0	0	2	1.4
	Between 3 and 6 months	8	4.8	2	9.1	6	4.1
	Between 6 months and 1 year.	7	4.2	0	0	7	4.8
	Between 1 and 5 years.	44	26.5	4	18.2	40	27.6
	Between 5 and 10 years.	40	24.1	5	22.7	36	24.8
	More than 10 years.	65	39.2	11	50	54	37.2
Job sector	Construction Sector	3	1.8	0	0	3	2.1
	Wholesale and retail sales	37	22.2	2	9.1	35	24.1
	Transport and warehousing	15	9.0	5	22.7	10	6.9
	Hospitality	21	12.6	4	18.2	17	11.7
	Financial and Insurance activities	21	12.6	3	13.6	18	12.4
	Professional, scientific, technique	5	3.0	2	9.1	3	2.1
	Administrative activities	21	12.6	3	13.6	18	12.4
	Public Administration, Defense	4	2.4	0	0	4	2.8
	Education	7	4.2	1	4.5	6	4.1
	Healthcare	7	4.2	0	0	7	4.8
	Others	26	15.6	2	9.1	24	16.6
Form of payment	Payment delegated by hiring company.	144	86.2	22	100	122	87.1
	Direct independent payment: self-employed.	18	10.8	0	0	18	12.4
	Direct payment by hiring company.	5	3.0	0	0	5	3.4

Table 3

Comparison of the different variables depending on the type of intervention

	Early intervention	Late intervention	<i>t</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i>
	(≤14 days) <i>n</i> (22) <i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)	(>14 days) <i>n</i> (145) <i>M</i> (<i>SD</i>)			
Time before beginning psychotherapy	9.82 (3.49)	53.21 (47.98)	-10.74	152,92	.001
Total duration of sick leave	96.90 (43.94)	177.59 (110,59)	-5,94	62,28	.001
Partial duration of sick leave	87 (44.31)	124 (96.98)	-2,874	50.88	.006
Time until return to work after the psychotherapy ends	- 15.40 (27.18)	17.86 (72.10)	-3.851	67.75	.001
Duration of psychotherapy	81 (42.83)	94.61 (71.56)	-0.867	164	.387

Table 4

Pre-treatment and post-treatment measures.

	Pre-treatment		Post-treatment		Pre-post $F_{(1,161)}$	η^2	Between groups	
	Early Treatment $M (SD)$	Late Treatment $M (SD)$	Early Treatment $M (SD)$	Late Treatment $M (SD)$			$F_{(1,161)}$	η^2
BAI	26.73(13.25)	28.54(11,48)	6.23(6,33)	9.29(8,21)	108.74**	.41	1.21	.007
BDI	27.82(11.24)	31.05(10.36)	5.95(6.49)	9.08(6,88)	166.08**	.51	.31	.001

Note: ** $p < .001$; BAI = Beck Anxiety Inventory; BDI = Beck Depression Inventory